

DOI: 10.31866/2617-2674.5.2.2022.269502
UDC 7.097:654.197

RELEVANCE OF ENTERTAINMENT SHOWS' STUDY ON TELEVISION

Alla Medvedieva^{1a}, Alona Novak^{2a}

¹ PhD in Art Studies, Associate Professor;
e-mail: Aamedvedeva@i.ua; ORCID: 0000-0003-1422-7743

² Master of Audiovisual Arts and Productions;
e-mail: alenanovak005@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0001-8012-9063

^a Kyiv University of Culture, Kyiv, Ukraine

Keywords:

entertaining TV shows;
TV programs;
TV;
programs on TV;
show business;
TV channel

Abstract

The purpose of the study is to analyze the relevance and feasibility of studying such a phenomenon as entertainment shows on Ukrainian television. It is also important to investigate how popular such content is in the Ukrainian context and the main factors that influence the degree of its popularity and analyze the current trends in entertainment TV shows. **The research methodology** consists in applying the following methods: theoretical – analysis of scientific sources of other researchers, a comparative approach to the analysis of TV programs and information sources; the generalization of the collected information, features of TV programs and trends; structural – the determination of the interdependence of structural components that influence the formation of the content of television programs, as well as the attitude of the viewer towards them; specific sociological – the preferences of the Ukrainian audience and why certain factors influence it are taken into account. **The scientific novelty is that** for the first time, the tendencies of TV shows are systematized and a comprehensive analysis of their development is carried out. Not only the Ukrainian context was taken into account, but a causal relationship was drawn between the state of Ukrainian television and world trends in entertainment programs. **Conclusions.** As a result of the study, the relevance of studying this area and the continuation of deeper research in this area have been analyzed. The current state of entertainment TV shows on Ukrainian television, the degree of popularity, and the main factors influencing it have been determined. It investigated how the global context influences the current trends of Ukrainian entertainment shows, the correlation with the tastes of the Ukrainian audience, and the results of such influence on the current state of the TV show.

For citation:

Medvedieva, A. and Novak, A. (2022). Relevance of Entertainment Shows' Study on Television. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, 5(2), pp.149-157.

Statement of the problem

Entertaining TV shows are a popular product among viewers on television. In addition, this product is such attractive content that on streaming services, which are now displacing traditional TV channels, the whole air is occupied by entertaining shows. Such content reaches the largest audience. Also, given the diversity of the show, any viewer can find a show to their liking. Some TV channels, such as STB, neglect news and movies in favor of entertaining programs. That is, channels with a certain thematic format were formed. Something like channels that show only news or purely movies around the clock. At the same time, among all TV genres, there are the entertaining programs that receive the least attention in research.

To understand the importance of researching entertaining TV shows, it is necessary to identify the main factors that determine their popularity. If such factors are significant and worth researching, they can be considered not only in the context of the causal relationship between the popularity of entertaining TV shows but also as socio-cultural factors that may be worth some research.

In the study of entertaining programs, it is necessary to pay attention to the trends of modern Ukrainian television. In the context of globalization, it is necessary to take into account the global context and consider foreign influences and trends in television. In addition, an important factor is that in the Soviet Union, the genre of entertaining television programs was not developed until the late 80s of the twentieth century. Moreover, television itself was not so popular until the 1990s, when televisions began to appear

in large numbers among consumers and finally supplanted radio.

Recent research and publications analysis

The number of publications researching television entertaining shows is small. Consider a few of them. U. V. Molenko in her article *Entertaining Programs on Ukrainian Television* (2015) most comprehensively raised the issue of the research relevance in this area. Kotliar S. and Harkusha N. in their work *Trends and Principles of the Impact of Entertaining Content on the Ukrainian Audience* (2019) considered the current state of entertaining TV shows and the main aspects of the impact of entertaining TV shows on the audience. A. Nedo's work *Entertaining nature of modern television: prospects and trends* not only global trends were described, but also how these trends affect the tastes of Ukrainian viewers. Putsyata I. *Aesthetics of words and images in social talk shows: the Ukrainian experience* (2018) also described the impact of global trends on the Ukrainian context of entertaining TV shows.

The purpose of the study is to determine whether the topic of entertaining TV shows on television is sufficiently researched and to analyze the relevance and feasibility of studying such a phenomenon as entertaining shows on Ukrainian television. It is also important to investigate how popular such content is in the Ukrainian context, and the main factors influencing the degree of its popularity. Because the popularity of entertaining TV shows determines whether they are worth exploring. It is also necessary to analyze current trends in entertaining TV shows. Trends in this area may be worth some research or there are

already enough scientific works to draw further conclusions about this area as a whole.

Main research material

Firstly, after analyzing the television programs of the largest Ukrainian channels, we can conclude that this segment is the most popular. It is important to take into account that sometimes entertaining TV shows are not a segment that dominates the channel's program. However, on any channel that is not focused on a specific topic (channels only with movies, purely with entertaining programs, or news channels), no other single TV genre can outnumber entertaining TV shows.

Y. V. Mulenko (2015, p.68) in her article *Entertaining Programs on Ukrainian Television* states: "The most popular Internet content platforms that displace television have absorbed the entertaining segment of the TV genre".

Given the above, the viewer is most interested in this genre. In addition, an interesting observation is that he is interested not only in contemplating but also in creating such content himself. This may be another explanation for why this genre is so popular (Mulenko, 2015, p.69).

It should be noted that S. Kotliar and N. Harkusha note in their study "Trends and principles of the impact of entertaining content on Ukrainian viewers": "For many researchers of the issues of entertainment television programs, the conclusions about the nature of the popularity of this genre are common. Among such factors are lightness, unobtrusiveness, and detachment. Humor is an important factor. Because there are jokes and irony in culinary and talk shows" (2019, p.86).

We should not forget about humorous shows, which are completely focused on

this. The factor of the spectator's interest in the lives of famous people must be taken into account. There are some programs about the life of the "stars". Famous people are also invited to the TV show because it is interesting for the viewer to see his idol in one or another new image and unusual situation for him. Shows that cover a person's private life are popular. For example, a show about a date, the exchange of a partner, real or directed family dramas, talk-shows, during which one or another problem of family life is discussed as individuals and a certain trend in society (Kotliar and Harkusha, 2019, p. 86).

It is also worth mentioning that Y. Shcherbyna in her article *Genre features of Entertaining Programs on Ukrainian Television* notes: "Entertaining TV shows can cover all areas of our lives. That's why their diversity is so great" (2015, p.256).

In addition, each show has its specific target audience and is broadcast at the most favorable time for that audience. For example, cooking shows take place in the morning and the afternoon. Because that's when people prepare to eat and, as an accompaniment, turn on a show. In the morning there is a show for housewives because at this time they are at home doing household chores.

According to Y. Shcherbyna, such programs, except for cooking, also cover issues of life, family life, useful advice for the house, and so on. Consider another example. In the morning before school, or the afternoon, when children come home from school, TV channels broadcast teen and children's shows. If such a show is put on the lunch program, the number of spectators will be minimal. This is because children are mostly in school, and the TV is watched by retirees or housewives (2015, p.257).

Given the above, entertainment shows can be selected for any demanding viewer. Such a program is created as if specially for him to be interested and keep for the whole time of broadcasting. Under such conditions, the influence of television on human life cannot be underestimated. It is necessary to understand that the flow of information coming to the viewer forms his worldview. And this affects his real behavior in decision-making and purchasing goods, as well as his ideological and political beliefs.

The average movie is better than the average TV show, but it may not reach the right audience. And if it does, it may not convey the idea embedded in it, because the audience is not so easy to accept a position highlighted in the film. Entertaining content is created for a specific target audience, so the information that should reach the viewer is selected specifically for him. At the same time, the methods of influence that are most effective for this audience are used. Of course, influence should be understood not so much as manipulation, but as the perception of content. Every audience needs the right presentation and the right messages. Under such conditions, the viewer will stay longer watching the program. A universal product will have much worse results than a product designed for a specific target audience.

We should not forget the fact that an entertaining TV program is primarily a means of organizing and spending leisure time, accordingly, it is designed to receive positive emotions from its target audience, so that the viewer can fully relax and get away from everyday life. In other words, the program strives for the maximum performance of the recreational function.

It is important to note the approach of S. Kotliar and N. Harkusha (2019,

p.87). They see the show as simple, fun content.

So, after analyzing the opinions of different researchers, we can conclude that common in their thoughts is that the show brings pleasure, relaxation, and removal from real problems. An entertaining program should satisfy the needs like getting pleasure and positive emotions, relieving tension, reducing anxiety, and moving away from reality.

The next argument is the variety of TV shows. E. Tsymbalenko (2013, p.209) in the article Tabloidization of Media Communications notes that today's entertaining content ranges from classic talk shows to extraordinary survival of stars in unusual conditions. This is the merit of television marketing. Because the task of the channel is to keep as many viewers as possible, and therefore to interest different categories of people. Of course, the channels are betting on the highest-rated entertaining TV programs in which they invest the most money. But the important thing is that they take into account the airtime of a certain audience.

In particular, after 18 p. m., the channels broadcast those programs that reach the largest audience. Mostly these are family shows that can be watched by both adults and children. When children are at school, retirees and housewives stay at home, so they are shown shows about life, cooking, dramas, and more. In the morning, the family cooks and eats, so the airtime is busy with cooking shows.

Except for the time of broadcasting, an important factor is the topic of a program. Because different viewers are interested in different topics. Teenagers will not watch cooking shows, and retirees will not watch programs about modern music. Therefore, it is important to note the thematic diversity of the show. Among

the main entertainment programs are the most popular ones: talk shows, cooking shows, transformation shows, secular chronicles, music programs, humorous programs, and show games. All kinds of entertaining shows are designed to satisfy a certain category of viewers. Culinary shows are created for housewives and cooking lovers. Show games are for teenagers. Humorous shows are made for all generations. Secular chronicles are mainly for lovers of fashion and secular life. Show transformation is for young people. Very often these genres are combined. The viewer can see a show with invited stars who do not just give interviews or cover a problem, as on a talk show, but cook, transform into various roles, and participate in interactive games.

The popularity of such shows is due to the fact that viewers want to see typical situations. And even more, he wants to know how his idol will behave in an unusual for him, but typical for the viewer's situation. The plot of the show is also an important factor. Not only comedy shows are popular, but also those that contain drama. Directed shows, in which guests argue or fight, have high ratings. It is a certain analog of TV series or movies. However, they do not require significant budgets and imagination when writing a script. Sometimes, of course, the guests of the show can create the appropriate effect without a script. Such shows are popular among retirees, women, and the elderly.

It should also be noted that I. Putsiata in his article *Aesthetics of Words and Images in Social Talk Shows: Ukrainian Experience* (2018) notes that the characteristic of modern shows is the presence of a live audience. Firstly, it creates interactions in the studio itself and removes the feeling of directing the show itself. Secondly, the

presence of people with whom the viewer identifies himself inspires confidence in him and as if unconsciously creates a friendly attitude to what is seen. Having kids at a children's show demonstrates to the child that they are happy to see. Consequently, the child spectator should be happy. Let's imagine that instead of children, adults will sit on the children's show as spectators. It is easy to predict a child's negative reaction (p.3).

Thirdly, regarding the trends of Ukrainian entertaining TV shows on television, it is worth noting the following. Throughout the history of Ukrainian television and entertaining shows, in particular, there is such a trend as Westernization. That is, borrowing existing models of the show. Of course, the broadcast is largely adapted to the local context. It should be added that this happens with movies, but more often with TV series. When the series about the Johnson conditional family in the post-Soviet space is adapted to the Ivanovs, leaving funny and dramatic situations. At the same time, the location and interior are changed, clichés branded for the region are added, and so on. In the field of talk shows, the situation is similar.

The dominance of Western products after the collapse of the Soviet Union explains why such a phenomenon as Westernization has taken place and has such a great impact on mass culture. The second factor is that in the United States and Europe, as locomotives of the genre, such shows have existed for decades. Therefore, they have passed the test of time. I.V. Cheremnykh in his article states: "It is easy to follow by someone else's example which product is most interesting to the audience. In addition, during this time the evolution of such programs took place, so they reached our viewers in the already developed form" (2006, p.175).

It should be added that the concept of Westernization needs to be expanded or replaced. Because borrowing comes not only from the United States and Europe. At the beginning of the zeros Latin American melodramas were very popular, and with them and similar shows. In recent years, according to I. V. Cheremnykh (2006, p.176), borrowings from Asia became popular. In particular, game TV shows from Korea and Japan are characterized by their extraordinary. Interestingly, they find their audience in Ukraine as well.

Another trend on Ukrainian television is the so-called "McDonaldization". This term refers to features that come from the corporate culture of the McDonald's fast food chain. Its features are also reflected on television. This trend can be described as follows. Creating content that aims to satisfy the needs of the viewer as soon as possible. That is, achieving the maximum result in the shortest time. In particular, it is best viewed through the prism of humorous and game shows.

The second characteristic feature of this trend is the use of tools to achieve the best results. That is the quality assessment standards.

Thus, A. Nedo (2016, p.40) in the article *Entertainment Nature of Modern Television: Perspectives and Trends* notes that over the years of the industry's existence, it has become clear that the most popular shows are those that are hosted by famous stars, that select the appropriate audience in the halls, and are shown at the best time for viewing by the target audience. Another feature is a kind of standardization.

For example, the show of talented vocalists *Voice of the Country* has analogs in most countries. If you follow this program in other countries, you can see that

they do not differ from each other. Because standardization creates brand recognition. Another important factor is that after watching the Ukrainian *Voice*, the viewer will watch a foreign one, and may become a fan of the entire franchise. The next feature is not positive. It consists in the primitivization of content. Simplicity is an advantage for the producer but offsets the quality of the product. On the other hand, due to low quality, you can create more such a product, spending less money on its shooting, directing, and so on.

As A. O. Nedo (2016, p.41) notes: "An interesting trend is the dominance of post-shows." The decision to split one reality show into two turned out to be very lucrative. Because now you can squeeze out more content from one script. Post-shows, according to A. Nedo, take the form of a talk show, which discusses the events that occurred during the main program. It is unlikely to attract new audiences but will keep the old ones and increase the time they spend on this channel.

A feature of Ukrainian television and a common feature for most types of entertaining programs is the mixing of genres. In particular, the presence of political issues in non-native programs. A talk show is a classic for this topic. However, now all comedy shows are not left out of the political context of today. In addition, sometimes politicians do not neglect to participate in game TV shows. They often appear at cooking or morning shows. According to the author, this is the result of Westernization. Participating politicians in such shows are common in the United States. Because the politician's task before the election is to please the electorate, he must move away from the boring image of seriousness and play the role of an ordinary person with his hobbies, sense

of humor, flaws, and so on. This is a good opportunity to raise your rating and remind yourself of the electorate. First of all, this is since in this way a politician can sway the viewer to his side, causing him sympathy as a fine fellow.

According to I. Putsyata, in the United States all started with the "Saturday night show" (2018). This is a classic talk show, where various celebrities talked to the host about themselves, current trends, and problems of the country and the world. However, to raise the ratings by keeping the audience, these shows used humor, non-standard tasks for guest stars, tricky questions, and more. It is clear that after that the politician changed radically in the eyes of the audience (p.4).

Conclusions

The topic of entertaining shows on television has been little studied and this is not a positive trend, given their impact on our lives. We have determined that TV shows are the most popular content on television. Therefore, they reach the largest audience. Also, an important factor is that each type of entertaining TV show is aimed at its specific audience. Due to this, the viewer is more interested in watching. Therefore, he will better accept information messages in the form of certain opinions or indirect advertising and so on. By researching the preferences of viewers, we can draw conclusions about certain social and cultural factors in society, current trends, and how to shape the media space in Ukraine. We have

seen that global trends directly affect the Ukrainian context, so when researching Ukrainian entertaining content on television, researchers will not fall out of the global context.

When researching the popularity of entertaining TV shows, you need to consider the following. Entertaining shows are designed to satisfy the needs of the audience in relaxation, rest, positive emotions, and more. The appropriate effect can be achieved through humor or drama. The show can be directed or, much less often, a real situation. TV channels are based on the target audience for which each show is created. Appropriate conditions are created for this audience in the form of the audience and the subject of the program. Broadcast time is selected for the target audience to capture as many viewers at a certain time when it is convenient for them to watch the program.

The main trends in the field of entertaining TV shows on television now include Westernization, McDonaldization, and the popularization of post-shows. Characteristic was the mixing of genres and the dominance of politics in programs of a completely different nature.

It can be concluded that it is necessary to increase the number of publications and research in this area. It mustn't be just about the industry as a whole. It is also worth researching some factors shaping the tastes of viewers, some trends, how these trends correlate with the global world context and what is the peculiarity of the preferences of Ukrainian viewers, and what trends are specific to Ukraine.

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АКТУАЛЬНІСТЬ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ РОЗВАЖАЛЬНИХ ШОУ НА ТЕЛЕБАЧЕННІ

Алла Медведєва^{1а}, Альона Новак^{2а}

¹ кандидат мистецтвознавства, доцент;

e-mail: aamedvedeva@i.ua; ORCID: 0000-0003-1422-7743

² магістр аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва;

e-mail: alenapovak005@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0001-8012-9063

^а Київський університет культури, Київ, Україна

Анотація

Мета дослідження – проаналізувати актуальність та доцільність вивчення розважальних шоу на українському телебаченні; дослідити попит на такий контент в українському контексті та визначити основні чинники, що впливають на ступінь його популярності; проаналізувати сучасні тенденції в розважальних телешоу. **Методологія дослідження** полягає у застосуванні таких методів: теоретичного – для аналізу наукових джерел інших дослідників; компаративного підходу до аналізу програм телеканалів та інформаційних джерел; узагальнення зібраної інформації, рис телепрограм та тенденцій; структурного – для визначення взаємозалежності структурних компонентів, які впливають на формування контенту телепрограм; конкретно-соціологічного – взято до уваги вподобання українського глядача та чому ті чи інші чинники впливають на нього. **Наукова новизна.** Вперше систематизовано тенденції телешоу та проведено комплексний аналіз їх розвитку. Взято до уваги не лише український контекст, а й проведено причинно-наслідковий зв'язок між станом українського телебачення та світовими тенденціями у розважальних передачах. **Висновки.** Проаналізовано актуальність вивчення зазначеної теми та окреслено перспективи подальших досліджень. Визначено сучасний стан розважальних телешоу на українському телебаченні, ступінь їх популярності та основні чинники, що на них впливають. Досліджено, яким чином світовий контекст впливає на сучасні тенденції українських розважальних шоу, їх кореляцію зі смаками українського глядача та наслідки такого впливу на сучасний стан телешоу.

Ключові слова: розважальні телешоу; телепрограми; телебачення; телевізійні передачі; шоу-бізнес; телеканал

